

Scalable Training for Sustainable Science: A Scoping Review of Research Software Engineering Education and Practice

Jasmin Hartanto ¹

Abstract: Research Software Engineering (RSE) is essential for sustaining high-quality scientific software, yet the field faces significant challenges related to sustainability, training, and best practices. This scoping review aims to identify current trends, challenges, best practices, and proposed solutions within RSE. A systematic search was conducted in the ACM and IEEE databases, yielding 36 initial results. After applying inclusion criteria and removing duplicates, 9 studies remained. Through backward and forward snowballing, 14 additional studies were identified, resulting in a final set of 24 papers. Our analysis reveals key trends, including the increasing emphasis on software sustainability, the need for structured training programs, and the role of collaboration in addressing technical and organizational challenges. Learning technologies are growing in RSE education, supporting scalable and accessible training solutions. We synthesize best practices, proposed solutions, and research gaps, highlighting future directions for improving RSE sustainability and impact.

Keywords: RSE, Research Software Engineering, Research Software Development, Education, Training, Review

1 Introduction

Research Software Engineering (RSE) has emerged as a critical discipline at the intersection of scientific research and software development. The UK Society of Research Software Engineering was founded in 2019, followed by similar initiatives in other countries, such as the German RSE Association (de-RSE), which was established to support knowledge sharing, training, and professional development. As modern research increasingly depends on complex computational tools and software systems, the quality, sustainability, and reproducibility of scientific outcomes are closely tied to the software that supports them. However, despite its growing importance, RSE remains underrecognized in many academic and institutional settings.

Researchers who develop software often face unique challenges that differ from those encountered in traditional software engineering. These include a lack of formal training in software engineering practices, ad hoc development processes, limited career pathways, and insufficient organizational support. Many research software engineers (RSEs) are self-taught, and structured education or training opportunities are still scarce. In many cases, research software is treated as a disposable byproduct rather than a long-term, valuable research

¹ RWTH Aachen University, Templergraben 55, 52062 Aachen, Germany, hartanto@cs.rwth-aachen.de, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5178-8497>

asset. At the same time, a growing number of initiatives, communities, and educational programs have emerged to support RSEs and promote sustainable practices.

In light of these developments, this scoping review aims to provide a structured overview of the current state of RSE. We investigate how RSE and the role of RSEs are defined in the literature, identify key challenges — particularly in training and sustainability — faced by practitioners, and synthesize proposed solutions, best practices, and community-driven efforts. Our goal is to contribute to the ongoing discourse around RSE and provide a foundation for further research and structural improvements in this field.

To this end, we conducted a systematic search in the ACM Digital Library and IEEE Xplore, supplemented by snowballing techniques and additional sources. In total, we analyzed 24 relevant studies, which we present and discuss in the following sections.

2 Research Method

The goal of this scoping review was to map the current landscape of RSE in terms of key challenges, best practices, training opportunities, and proposed solutions. Following established approaches to scoping reviews, we conducted a systematic and iterative process of literature selection, screening, and analysis. This included database searches, snowballing techniques, and the inclusion of grey literature to ensure comprehensive coverage of the topic.

We conducted a systematic search in two major digital libraries relevant to computing and engineering research: ACM Digital Library and IEEE Xplore. The search string used was:

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("research software engineering" OR "research software development")  
AND (educat* OR training OR "life cycle") AND sustainab*
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This expression was designed to capture literature discussing RSE in relation to training, education, software life cycles, and sustainability. The search was last conducted on February 14, 2025, yielding 31 results from ACM and 5 results from IEEE, totaling 36 initial records.

The following multi-step screening process was applied to identify relevant studies:

1. **Deduplication and Initial Filtering:** We removed duplicates and excluded non-research content such as entire conference proceedings and books, based on the assumption that relevant individual articles within those would have already appeared in the search. All results were already in English. After this filtering step, 27 studies remained.
2. **Title, Keyword, and Abstract Screening:** We then performed a relevance scan of titles, abstracts, and keywords. Papers not aligned with our focus on challenges, training, best practices, or sustainability in RSE were excluded. This step reduced the dataset to 12 studies.

3. **Full-Text Review:** Each of the remaining 12 papers underwent full-text analysis to assess whether they provided substantial insights into RSE-specific topics. This step resulted in a final set of 9 core papers.

To enrich our dataset and mitigate the limitations of database indexing, we used backward and forward snowballing on the reference lists and citation trails of the 9 core papers. This process yielded 10 additional relevant studies.

In a final step, we included 4 additional studies and 1 project website that were known to the authors or identified during exploratory work, but did not appear in the original search or snowballing. These resources were deemed highly relevant to the research questions. A visual overview of the selection process is provided in Fig. 1.

Abb. 1: Paper selection process.

3 Results

The following section contains the findings from our literature search. We searched for differing definitions of the term *research software engineering* as well as of the role of a *research software engineer*, the identified challenges, solutions to those challenges as well as emerging best practices. Lastly, we identified further interesting details from the studies.

3.1 Definitions of RSE

There are differing definitions around the term *research software engineering*, emphasizing different aspects of the whole concept, as shown in table 1. As some studies feature multiple aspects as important, they are counted in more than one category. Predominantly, RSE is defined as the development of software for research purposes, as featured in 11 studies. That includes software supporting research activities, and any software used and developed in the context of research. Seven studies have not explicitly stated their definition; however, it can be read from the context that the definition of RSE is the same as mentioned before:

development of software for research purposes. Other definitions lay the focus on the creation of new knowledge, as featured in three studies, and requiring domain-specific knowledge, as featured in two studies. Two studies discuss using software engineering practices in the research context, and one study does not only restrict the scope to research but to any profession that the developer practices, e.g., finances, or biology.

Definition: Development of software ...	Appearances
... for research purposes	[Co18] [Fe25] [Ne23] [MMI14] [VSH20] [Co21] [HSM18] [Wi14] [An20] [Go24] [JH18]
... for research purposes (implicitly)	[Ka19] [Wi16b] [Br17] [Wi16a] [Sa13] [PP12] [HS17]
... that leads to new knowledge	[Gu21] [Ji17] [Ha09]
... requiring domain-specific knowledge	[Wi14] [Ha09]
... using SE practices in research context	[Go24] [DFH24]
... for one's professional goals	[Se07]

Tab. 1: Differing definitions of *Research Software Engineering*.

Equally, the role of the *research software engineer* is defined differently in the selected studies, as shown in table 2. In 13 studies, RSEs are displayed as researchers who develop software, in three of those only given implicitly. On the other hand, two studies feature the role of RSEs as professional software engineers who work with or for researchers to develop research software. In the remaining eight studies, the term is used for both roles simultaneously.

Definition	Appearances
Researcher who develops software	[Fe25] [VSH20] [HSM18] [Wi14] [Ji17] [Wi16b] [Ha09] [Sa13] [HS17] [JH18]
Researcher who develops software (implicitly)	[PP12] [Se07] [Wi16a]
SE who develops software with/for researchers	[Co18] [Ka19]
Combination of both	[Ne23] [Gu21] [Co21] [Br17] [An20] [Go24] [DFH24] [MMI14]

Tab. 2: Differing definitions of the role of the *Research Software Engineer*.

3.2 Identified Challenges

Many challenges in the context of RSE have been identified and are presented in table 3, with the most prominent being a lack of knowledge regarding software engineering practices, as featured in 13 studies. This leads to ad hoc development of the research software [Ka19] [MMI14] [Co21] [HSM18], often in isolation [JH18], without using version control [HS17] [HSM18] or documentation [HS17] [HSM18]. As a reason, it is stated that RSEs are mainly self-taught as software engineering practices often come up short in their formal education [VSH20] [Ha09] [Wi16a] [Se07] [DFH24]. The next issue stated by eleven studies is the

view on research software as only a byproduct of scientific results, with a lack of incentives to write sustainable software. As research results are mostly assessed based on the novelty of the results [JH18], publications and citations thereof, the software receives little priority. This however leads to the third challenge which is the unreliability of results, featured in five studies. Research software often remains unpublished and poorly written, coded in isolation without review [JH18], possibly imposing a threat to the validity of the results because of the impossibility to reproduce the results. On the organizational level, there is a clear lack of resources to sustain software long-term, as pointed out by five studies, due to the reason that research projects have fixed funding schedules [Fe25] [HSM18][An20], and writing software with a sustainable approach tends to take an extended period of time [Wi16b]. Another issue identified by four studies on this level is the lack of a proper career path for RSEs, likewise due to the lack of funding, and the view on scientific software as a byproduct in the research process. Furthermore, three studies demonstrate that due to the exploratory nature of research, many traditional software engineering methods, such as requirements engineering up front [Fe25] or standard testing procedures [Ha09], are not suited for RSE. Lastly, one study explains that the rapid change of the hardware landscape and the difference of hardware resources complicate the process.

Challenge	Appearances
Lack of Knowledge	[Ne23] [Ka19] [MMI14] [VSH20] [Co21] [HSM18] [Wi14] [Ji17] [Wi16b] [Ha09] [Br17] [Wi16a] [Se07] [HS17] [DFH24]
Software as a byproduct	[Co18] [Ne23] [MMI14] [VSH20] [Gu21] [HSM18] [Br17] [Se07] [PP12] [An20] [JH18]
Unreliability of the results	[Fe25] [Wi14] [Wi16b] [Sa13] [JH18] [DFH24]
Lack of resources	[Fe25] [Ne23] [MMI14] [HSM18] [An20]
No RSE career path	[Ne23] [HSM18] [Br17] [Se07]
Disparity between RSE/traditional SE	[Fe25] [Ha09] [DFH24]
Rapid change of hardware landscape	[An20]

Tab. 3: Identified challenges in the RSE process.

3.3 Role of Communities

Communities have turned out to play an important role in RSE. The findings of our survey are shown in table 4. Above all, the importance of community efforts by volunteers, such as Software Carpentry, was emphasized by six studies as they aid RSEs in learning the necessary skills to build sustainable research software [An20]. The next prominent aspect of communities is to provide a forum for knowledge sharing, support and networking, as featured in five studies. The role of overarching associations above organizational level was mentioned in three studies, as several organizations have been formed on national as well as international level to address the issues in RSE and promote change in the scientific community [Ka19]. One example is the deRSE, the German national RSE association

[de24], as it provides information about everything concerning RSEs in Germany as well as teaching and learning opportunities for those working in the field and looking for education opportunities. The next aspect in regard to RSE communities is that if developers decide to use open-source methods, they allow a community to be built around their research project and authorize contributors to become stakeholders in the process [Ne23]. This community role was featured in two studies and demands transparency and cooperation in the development process between the community members, actively allowing the cultivation of the project as a community effort.

Community aspect	Appearances
Importance of volunteer organizations	[An20] [Go24] [Br17] [Wi16a] [Wi14] [Co21]
Knowledge sharing and support	[Co18] [Co21] [HSM18] [HS17] [Go24]
Associations above organizational level	[Fe25] [Ka19] [Co21] [de24]
Research project communities	[Co21] [Go24]

Tab. 4: Aspects of the role of communities in the RSE process.

3.4 Best Practices

Practice	Appearances
Software Engineering vs. RSE Skills	[Fe25] [MMI14] [Se07] [Wi16a] [JH18] [DFH24]
Programming tips	[Sa13] [PP12] [Wi14] [Wi16b]
Open-Source	[MMI14] [PP12] [An20] [Ji17]
Institutional support	[Ka19] [MMI14] [Co21] [JH18]
Teaching/Learning	[Wi16a] [JH18] [HS17] [Ha09] [de24] (more dlr papers?)
Project organization	[MMI14] [Ji17]

Tab. 5: Best practices for sustainable RSE.

Due to the lack of suitable solutions to the challenges presented, many best practices have emerged. The results can be sorted into six categories, as shown in table 5.

In a comparison between traditional software engineering and RSE skills, some skills can be adopted, whereas others are not suitable for RSE. Six studies investigate the differences between the two disciplines. There is no consensus on how to structure an RSE process yet [MMI14], formal software engineering techniques do not work on the RSE process [Wi16a], and the specific requirements of research software often lead to an iterative development approach [Se07]. The nature of RSE prohibits traditional requirements engineering, so research-specific requirements engineering techniques have to be developed [Fe25]. There is no consensus yet on how and which requirements engineering techniques are applicable [JH18], however, lightweight and modern approaches are recommended [DFH24]. Traditional testing methods also do not work, due to the fact that results are found exploratively [Se07], so testing without test oracles [Fe25], such as machine-learning techniques [JH18] is recommended. Furthermore, instead of using general-purpose

languages, domain-specific languages are suggested as they limit their expressiveness to a particular domain [DFH24].

Four studies offer practical guidance on programming and data handling that RSEs can adopt. Sandve et al. [Sa13] provide a list of ten rules around best data manipulation practices to make research results reproducible. In addition to general programming tips, Prlić and Procter [PP12] give recommendations on how to handle and develop open-source scientific software. Wilson et al. [Wi14] recommend a list of best practices based on experience from *Software Carpentry* that do not guarantee success but will reduce errors if introduced over time. Beyond that, they provide another list of 'good enough' practices [Wi16b] consisting of a minimum set of explicit practices that every researcher can and should adopt. They address practices around data management, software, collaboration, project organization, tracking changes, manuscripts, and more.

Open-source is recommended in four studies, to create a software ecosystem [MMI14] or a community around the research software project [Ji17], or to be able to publish and distribute it freely [PP12] [An20].

Four studies recommend best practices around the research organization: How well-designed a research organization supports sustainable RSE depends on its leadership and not only on the researchers themselves [MMI14]. Engaging dedicated software engineers as mobile long-term staff for research projects [Ka19] [JH18] can aid in programming processes as well as in organizing less-experienced team members. Cohen et al. [Co21] present four pillars of RSE that can help get an overview on how RSE is supported in an institution: Software development (if common software development best practices are followed), communities (how well the communication between developers is and how knowledge sharing is performed), training (continuous learning of new techniques and tools), and policy (the view on RSE as a career path).

Learning and teaching opportunities for RSEs are very important for continuous training and knowledge sharing. The general need was already presented in the challenges identified in section 3.2. Four studies and one website address practices around it. Training opportunities can be formal or around peer learning. Peer learning and knowledge sharing between RSEs is rated highly [HS17] and even higher than formal education in software engineering [Ha09]. In comparison, classes from communities such as *Software Carpentry* have identified practices around teaching classes, e.g., the time has to be appropriate for learning (knowledge from a week-long course may not hold in one's head), or workshops in pre-tied groups work well, especially for underrepresented groups. Organizations of any level can offer training possibilities for RSEs. One example is *deRSE*, the national RSE organization in Germany. They offer a list of possibilities where (aspiring) RSEs can find learning or teaching opportunities. [de24]

Lastly, organizational details around the implementation of the research software are covered in two studies. Using software roadmaps to plan which features are developed at what time

prevents ad hoc development [MMI14]. Besides, planning the project around the general values and practices of open-source is recommended [Ji17].

3.5 Solutions

There are institutions and existing research software projects that have successfully overcome challenges and problems and have found specific solutions to their problems. In addition, many solutions are recommended that have a broader scope than solving individual problems and demand a structural change in the RSE landscape. Both the proven concepts and the structural recommendations are shown in table 6.

Solutions	Appearances
<i>DLR Software Engineering Initiative</i>	[VSH20] [HSM18] [HS17]
<i>Software Carpentry</i>	[Wi14] [Wi16a]
<i>Python Tutor</i>	[Gu21]
RSE as a career path	[Co18] [Co21] [Br17] [An20] [Go24]
Better funding for sustainable projects	[Co21] [An20]
Add credit to software	[Co18] [Co21]
Integrate training into education	[An20] [Go24]
Certificates	[Go24]
Promote volunteer communities	[An20]

Tab. 6: Proven concepts and structural recommendations as solutions to the RSE challenges.

3.5.1 Proven Concepts

In addition to the many best practices that are recommended to help overcome the challenges that have emerged in the context of RSE, there are some concepts that have already been proven over the years and showcase an example of how good RSE can be achieved. There are three examples in the selected studies. Three studies focus on the *DLR Software Engineering Initiative*, two studies on *Software Carpentry* classes and one study features *Python Tutor*.

The *DLR Software Engineering Initiative* provides an example of how RSE is handled successfully within a research organization in four studies. To equip their researchers with the appropriate tools to develop sustainable software, they offer software engineering guidelines and checklists for iterative development [VSH20], they provide their employees with the essential software engineering tools such as version control and offer opportunities for knowledge exchange. Therefore, they run a dedicated wiki for software engineering topics along with active support tools, conduct knowledge exchange workshops, and offer regular training [HS17] [HSM18]. They furthermore provide a pool of consultants [HSM18] whose help the researchers can utilize. However, Von Kurnatowski et al. [VSH20] note that

despite the efforts of the DLR, there remains a mismatch between theory and practice, as not all guidelines and opportunities provided are followed and taken by the researchers.

Software Carpentry offers classes for one or multiple persons who decide to improve their skills in the craft of software engineering. They are offering an increasing number of workshops internationally. RSE often demands domain-specific skills, but the authors state that their 'real aim isn't to teach any specific tool: it's to teach computational competence.' [Wil16a] Learnings that they have made over the years of teaching include using live coding, opening everything that is not personally sensitive information to the public, or having the participants take notes collaboratively. Furthermore, they argue for having volunteers as teachers and asking for a small participation fee in their classes to lower the risk of no-shows.

A different solution comes from the *Python Tutor* software project, which has been developed and continuously improved by one developer alone over the course of more than ten years, featuring a user base of millions of users [Gu21]. The corresponding developer presents guidelines for user experience (ease of use, programming with the mindset of a professional software engineer, enabling sharing of the user-generated content instead of hosting it and minimizing user options), software architecture design (minimizing dependencies, single-developer workflow, statelessness in regard to server states, and the use of older technologies for stability) and software development workflows (single-developer workflow in academic settings, specificity instead of generality, and the focus on the essential details instead of working only on user issues).

3.5.2 Structural Solutions

Identified as a challenge before, the introduction of a general career path for RSEs is proposed to bridge the gap between researchers and software engineers, as recommended in five studies. Offering permanent jobs in academic positions instead of relying solely on short-term contracts would offer more incentive to professional software developers to take up such positions.

In research projects, however, funding, especially long-term, presents a challenge because it depends on the policies of the funding bodies. Therefore, two studies recommend that funders take software sustainability into account when deciding which projects to fund.

Recognizing the importance of software as a research output would counteract the view on software as a byproduct of publications. Thus, two studies recommend adding credit to research software.

Providing skill certificates is another approach, featured in one study, that is already being employed in some research fields, such as bioinformatics and high-performance computing [Go24]. Adapting this approach to more fields could help overcome the lack of knowledge.

By establishing skill trees with different skills that an RSE should possess in different fields or as general knowledge, success in learning these skills can be measured.

Two further suggestions are promoting the building of volunteer communities, featured in one study, and integrating specific training into the education of researchers, featured in two studies. The role of communities has been evaluated in section 3.3, where the point of creating a community effort out of a research project to help its sustainability was made. Training in software engineering can be incorporated into different stages of academic education [Go24].

3.6 Interesting Details

The following section presents details from the studies that go beyond the scope of our review but add interesting aspects for our future work.

3.6.1 Researcher Mindset

Currently, research software is mainly built to validate an idea, and is contradicted by the idea of long-term maintenance [Gu21]. However, all the extra resources that flow into writing software (possibly with poor quality) repeatedly would negate this contradiction again, but only thinking in short-term contracts, some researchers may not see the benefits of sustainable research software. As software outlives a project, it can be seen as a "living artifact"[MMI14] or a project legacy even after the project ended. Good research software quality further leads to trustworthiness and transparency [Sa13].

Formal education in software engineering is mostly general and researchers often do not see the need for formal training in software engineering practices. One problem appears to be a missing transition between general programming constructs and writing software to solve specific research domain problems. [Se07] The need for good practices may arise too far into the development process [Ha09]. Changing this mindset proves to be no easy task: 'Change is hard and if researchers don't see those benefits quickly enough to justify the pain, they will almost certainly switch back to their old way of doing things.' [Wi16b] As scientific software follows different characteristics and constraints than traditional software, any developed approach should follow the distinct characteristics of scientific software to be adopted by scientists [Fe25].

3.6.2 Stakeholder Involvement

There are many different stakeholders in research software projects. Anzt et al. [An20] provide a list of possible stakeholders: The general public, the domain researchers, dedicated

RSEs, organizations, funding organizations, geopolitical units, infrastructure units, industry and independent developers. Each of them has disparate needs for the research process and different incentives in RSE which can be targeted utilizing specific measures.

As mentioned in section 3.3, building communities around research projects can aid in the process of sustainable RSE. A dedicated community with active developers becomes a stakeholder in the process with its own incentives to develop the software in a sustainable fashion and maintain it that way [Ne23]. However, this demands not only openness of the research project creators but also full transparency in every aspect of project management. To build an active developing community around a research project, it is imperative to give community developers a voice in decision-making.

Currently, the requirements for the software are documented in proposal and publication papers and form a foundation which the funding bodies and the researchers have agreed on together. If software sustainability is not prioritized in those papers, it is often up to the RSEs to build the software in a sustainable fashion from their own intrinsic interest. However, Jiménez et al. [Ji17] argue that stakeholders who are not developers themselves can also drive the development of better software by providing an external incentive. Haupt et al. [HSM18] support this argument with an example from organizational leadership. By providing an official incentive for better RSE, developers are also encouraged to claim support if opportunities are offered.

4 Conclusion

In this systematic literature review, we aimed to gain an overview of the current RSE landscape. Therefore, we found 24 relevant sources and analyzed them concerning differing definitions of the subject and its role, the main challenges and corresponding best practices and solutions as well as the role of RSE communities.

We identified seven primary challenges: A lack of knowledge, the view of software as a byproduct of science, unreliability of the results due to poor code quality, a lack of resources to support sustainable RSE, the lack of a proper RSE career path, disparity between traditional and RSE methods and requirements, as well as a rapid change of the hardware landscape. To confront these challenges, we analyzed the selected studies for proven concepts and recommendations for structural changes that must be made to support sustainable RSE. Furthermore, we identified best practices that have helped RSEs address these challenges in the past without the need for structural change. These include methods and skills that have been adapted to RSE in comparison to traditional software engineering, explicit tips for programming and data handling, using open-source, best practices for institutional support, teaching and learning in formal (courses) and informal ways (peer-learning), and project organization. Furthermore, we examined the role of communities on different levels: The general role of communities as a forum for knowledge sharing and support, communities

around a research project, volunteer efforts, and associations above organizational level such as national or international RSE societies.

Finally, we summarized interesting details in all selected studies that were not included in the former sections but must be taken into account when examining how the current situation can be improved. This involved the researcher's mindset when writing software and the (non-)willingness to adapt to new methods and practices, as well as thoughts on stakeholder involvement.

5 Future Work

From our findings, we identified a general problem: The incapacity of many researchers working in the field of RSE, counteracted by an abundance of different guidelines and best practices, but no central, easy-to-follow solution. Different knowledge levels and possibilities provided by the research institutions overcomplicate the situation further. Due to the lack of tangible solutions, the complexity of solving the whole problem at once becomes apparent. Therefore, we strive for a solution to collect researchers of different knowledge levels and build a foundation for sustainable RSE. Our next steps will be conducting interviews with different stakeholders in the RSE process to further specify the identified challenges with specific problems and lack of practice.

Furthermore, we included the deRSE in our review, the German national RSE association, that provides many teaching and learning resources [de24] for RSEs. In other countries, associations and communities like this exist as well. Competencies and necessary RSE skills are collected in different task forces. Bringing these guidelines and findings together and evaluating their feasibility with RSEs from different fields can support in splitting theory from practice to bolster the foundation the we aim to build.

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